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STUDY OF FINANCIAL RETAIL DISTRIBUTION – INDIAN SCENARIO

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ABSTRACT

These are exciting times for financial retail sector in India. Along with the massive volumes that the markets here can provide, there are also forecasts of rapid growth expected in the banking and insurance sector over the next 5 years. The total revenue in the insurance sector is over 55,000 million US dollars in 2009 and a projected CAGR of 17.2% for the next 5 years. Banking sectors with operating assets of over 550 billion US dollars and a forecasted CAGR of about 18% for the next 5 years is expecting a similar growth trend. Banking and Insurance together form around 92% of the total financial retail industry. Although mutual funds and equity related investments are catching up in popularity but over the next 5 year Banking & Insurance are still expected to be major areas of growth.

The predicted growth depends on how effectively the industry ramps up its distribution network at a low cost. The whitepaper looks at the state of the distribution networks for the sector, specifically banking & Insurance, and proposes the way forward for rising up to the challenges of meeting the forecasted opportunities.

Keywords: Retail Banking, Insurance, CAGR, Incentive Management, Sales Process

Introduction:

Analysis Approach & Methodology

To gain detailed understanding of the sector, the methodology used was to talk to industry experts and professionals with vast amount of experience in the field along with different market researches available. The targeted persons who were interviewed include Regional Sales Heads to sales executives.

The research was performed to understand channel operations of 8 financial institutions. The organizations which were considered, deal in the area of Banking Products, Mutual funds Insurance, and other financial services. The companies which were a part of this analysis were Large PSU and Private Banks as well as Insurance organizations, Life Insurance Corporation and some small brokerage firms. Primary research was the key source of collecting information. SMEs (Subject matter experts) and industry analysts were interviewed in this study too. The collective experience of those professionals who were interviewed is over 150 years in the financial industry.

Choice of Channels

The different channels selected for distribution in financial sector vary based on the complexity of the products sold and also on the service level that required to be provided during the sales process.

Fig1 - Channels

Internet-based sales and indirect channels of sales like outbound calls etc. are useful for plain vanilla products but standalone generally fail to offer an effective way for sales for most of the financial products specifically in Indian context. The primary channels still remains independent sales agencies, company’s own agents and direct sales teams. The other channels are leveraged mostly to support these primary channels & capture specific segments which are tech savvy and time crunched.

We observed that the choice of channel in the Indian context is not only dependant on the complexity of product but also depends on how well the channel supports organizational goals and objectives of cost effectiveness, scalability in terms of ability to capture targeted segments, customer satisfaction, Sales conversion targets, faster turnaround times and still manage to be profitable.

Fig2 – Channel dependency

The cost was a major factor which we empirically found was weighted at around 30% (approx.) by most of the decision makers when making their choices.

The cost drivers for companies own direct sales teams (DST) & direct sales agency (DSA) or outside mercenaries show a varied pattern. The DST’s are driven by more fixed costs and are less flexible while the DSAs are flexible but are generally more sales expensive channels for sales.

The table below summarises other issues which a company needs to focus on before making a choice of sales mix through these afore-mentioned two channels.

Fig3 – Direct Sales Frameworks

Sales Process

The process is built of individual building blocks and before we move into looking at insurance and banking sector individually it would be helpful to understand these building blocks.

Fig4 – Sales Process

The sales operations processes for Indian banking & financial companies are getting more complex by its size, volume and the vast geography and diversity. The usage of multiple channels and agency distribution have created meshed interfaces for all these processes which require added management intervention and create possible blind spots that can be detrimental to the operation of the entire supply chain. Aligning all these processes in line for a strategic growth is imperative in changing times. Each of the above building blocks performs the function of seamlessly integration of operations with the growth strategy and none of them can be neglected at all.

Insurance

There are two primary channels for distribution of insurance In India, tied agents and agencies. Almost 80% of sales materialize through the tied agents of the company the rest 20% is broken up into agency sales and corporate brokers.

The sector is highly regulated with strict conditions required as per IRDA guidelines. The commission rates for agents are determined by IRDA based on the products. Life Insurance Company of India still has an 80% market share in India. The private players are improving their positions but still face a major channel of creating a network for sales.

The channels are reviewed on 3 parameters in the sector:

- **Volume** of policies sold
- **Premium** on each policy
- **Persistence:** This basically means the continuation of the policy after 1st year. (Since most of the policies are profitable only after completion of first year)

Acquiring agents is expensive and training/enabling them as per the IRDA guidelines adds additional constraints on the companies in terms of cost and time.

The few pain points that were discussed during interaction with sales managers in selling insurance in India are:

- Lack of awareness of the importance of insurance is the biggest challenge faced in the distribution of Insurance in India. With the changing lifestyles and growth of ambition oriented middle class this problem is growing intense. The penetration of insurance products in rural parts of the country is much better than in urban areas.
- Attrition rate poses other challenges :
 - The agents cannot grow beyond their natural market (family/friends/relatives)
 - The effective tenure of more than 95% of the agents is not more than 3 years.
 - Need for constant hiring
 - Sales pipeline management is an issue which needs to be taken care
- Managing the productivity of Sales managers is also an area of major concern. The sales managers have a target of daily sales calls that they need to target and achieve. In the current scenario there is no way of verifying if this is already been done which is causing a big challenge.

Banking

In the banking sector, the area of focus was on asset products i.e. loans and credit cards since the liability products are restricted to be sold only through banks outlets.

Till 2009 Sales agencies were a primary sales channel in this sector. ICICI for example achieved a significant amount of growth using this channel. After the economy started showing positive signs of recovery from the recession and the certainty it brings the focus is more on shifting from DSAs to DSTs. Though this is true DSAs are here to stay with their role might be little less important in the future. Most of the companies let DSAs and DSTs compete in the same market amongst themselves to put pressure on them to perform and achieve better results.

The banking organizations face similar problems to that of insurance but they have certain additional elements inherent to the specific industry.

- Of all the prospects/opportunities who apply for credit around 40% are rejected. (Adverse Selection)
- Though Technology is leveraged, there are multiple disjointed systems which prevent full utilization of available IT support.
- The operational efficiency is low with high lead times for delivery.

Suggested Improvements

Primary Risk Assessment

Sales team members generally would like to pass on as many prospects as possible to increase their chances of approvals which can add to this redundancy to the process.

One way to manage this is having approval rate as one of the criteria for final incentive calculation & payment.

The problem with having approval rate as criteria is the inability of the sales teams to accurately measure the approval probability of the client. Reasons for that might be:

Inadequate training on risk assessment parameters

- Dynamic nature of change of these parameters
- Prospects withholding information
- No access to CIBIL and other such databases used during agencies
- Information on possible deviances which are again highly dynamic

Some of the solutions to this problem would be periodic updates on the parameters and deviation criteria, training on primary risk assessment & measurement and access to repositories used for verification.

Leads and Daily Activity reports:

- The leads are currently passed on through paper printouts or periodic phone calls/emails.
- Even if the prospect is close to where the sales person is, in some case the DSE would need to report to the branch office to get the list.
- The daily activity report has the same problem.

These types of reports can be stored on an electronic platform and monitored.

Also having it registered on an electronic format would result in easy retrieval and analytics for management reporting.

Incentive Management and Contests:

- Effective management of Incentive plans will lead to a more motivated sales force
- These programs can be used as tools to drive employee behaviour to achieve larger corporate goals & objectives
- Sales Contests can be additional sweetener for the sales force and can help organizations achieve short term targets.

One Stop Solution:

Fig5– One Stop Solution

There seems to be a scope for rolling out a tool which will:

- Combine all the above mentioned requirements on integrated platform
- Provide knowledge management portal for keeping the DSE updated about new regulations & compliance and competitor products which might aid them in selling.

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